

HITL, ML, and the Bible

Leveraging High-Quality Data from a Digital Scholarly Edition

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Introduction

This paper examines how data from the Digital Scholarly Edition (DSE) of N.F.S. *Grundtvig's Works* is employed to develop a tool that automates the identification of Bible references—a crucial yet time-consuming task in textual scholarship. We address the core question: how can data from a DSE be harnessed to streamline and partially automate editorial processes? By integrating a Human-in-the-Loop (HITL) approach, we demonstrate how Machine Learning (ML) can transform rich, annotated DSE data into a form of “gold”, enhancing both efficiency and accuracy in scholarly editing workflows. Our previous work has shown the advantages of incorporating ML in both the production and computational analysis of DSE materials (Baunvig 2023; Rasmussen et al. 2023). In this paper, we present the workflow, discuss challenges, and share preliminary results, illustrating how HITL strategies bridge the gap between traditional philological methods and computational techniques.

N.F.S. Grundtvig and Grundtvig's Works

N.F.S. Grundtvig (1783–1872)—poet, pastor, politician influenced by the romantic movement—played a central role in 19th-century Danish nation-building and the development of modern Danish Christianity. *Grundtvig's Works* is Denmark's largest humanities research initiative, supported by the national financial act and underscoring Grundtvig's continued cultural importance. His corpus encompasses a wide range of genres: nearly 1,600 hymns and songs; historical and mythological essays; political tracts; and linguistic studies and editions of Old Icelandic and Old English literature. This diversity is captured in the DSE, which includes 1,073 works published between 1804 and 1872—more than 37,000 print pages and 4 million words.

The texts are prepared using OCR and encoded in TEI P5-compliant XML. To date, 59% of the corpus is fully annotated, and the entire dataset is projected to be completed by December 31, 2029. The data is publicly available on GitHub (<https://github.com/centre-for-humanities-computing/grundtvig-data>), alongside a dedicated XML parser for third-party data exploration (<https://github.com/centre-for-humanities-computing/GrundtvigParser>).

Annotations and Bible References

Bible references feature prominently throughout Grundtvig’s writings. At present, 56% of the edition’s material includes 10,451 annotated Bible references, all identified and categorized by experts at Aarhus University. These annotations fall into five categories (custom-developed for this project and not part of standard TEI):

1. **Quotes:** Direct quotations from the Bible
2. **References:** Passages with language signaling a specific biblical verse
3. **Allusions:** Passages thematically connected to the Bible, though not linguistically similar
4. **E.g. References:** Cases where multiple identical verses could apply, with a single verse chosen as an example
5. **Norm Form:** Explicit citations (e.g., “Rom. 8:19”) Unlike other categories, 'Norm Form' specifically refers to instances where Bible verses are cited explicitly with book, chapter, and verse numbers, providing a clear and unambiguous link to the biblical source

To annotate the remaining texts, we aim to leverage AI and ML methods. Such approaches are feasible only because we have access to high-quality, carefully aligned data from the existing annotations. We are currently developing a Bible Annotation Tool tailored for Grundtvig’s corpus. This tool identifies sentences bearing similarities to specific Bible verses and assigns confidence scores indicating the strength of the textual match. To achieve this, it must rely on the version of the Bible Grundtvig himself used—the 1787 Danish edition—rather than modern translations. Differences in vocabulary and phrasing underscore why this historical edition is essential.

Although general Text Reuse Detection tools (e.g., *Passim*, an open-source tool) can identify references, they are not optimized for our specialized Danish-language corpus and its historical Bible text. Instead, we are creating a customized solution inspired by Text Reuse Detection methods but trained explicitly on our annotated corpus and the 1787 Bible.

The Process: Developing the Bible Annotation Tool

We are currently transcribing the 1787 *Biblia* via Transkribus, an AI-based platform for handwritten text recognition. The resulting digital version will serve as the foundation dataset for our annotation tool.

Once transcription is complete, we will train a ML model using both the transcribed Bible and the existing annotated Grundtvig corpus. Training data will include examples of direct quotations, paraphrases, and allusions to ensure the model can handle varied forms of text reuse. After initial training, domain experts—scholars of Grundtvig and his historical context—will evaluate the model’s outputs and provide feedback to improve its accuracy.

Once refined, the model will be applied to unannotated texts, flagging potential Bible references with a similarity score (e.g., 60%). Expert editors will review these suggestions, accepting, modifying, or rejecting the annotations as needed. Special attention will be paid to allusions and ambiguous cases with multiple possible biblical sources. Ultimately, the HITL-based tool will serve as an editorial assistant, expediting the annotation process while preserving human expertise and oversight.

Methodological Innovation in Textual Scholarship

This project exemplifies how the integration of ML and HITL approaches can serve as a model for sustainable innovation in digital humanities research. By offering a framework for semi-automated annotation that complements—rather than supplants—traditional humanistic expertise, it demonstrates a pathway towards more efficient, reproducible, and scalable scholarly workflows. This methodological synergy can empower digital humanists to engage more deeply with complex corpora, refine analytical protocols, and ultimately broaden the scope and impact of their interpretive endeavors. This approach not only enhances annotation accuracy in *Grundtvig's Works* but also offers a scalable model for similar textual corpora, fostering new opportunities in comparative studies across historical editions and digital archives.

Conclusion

In sum, this paper illustrates how integrating machine learning with human expertise can transform editorial workflows in textual scholarship. By leveraging high-quality data from the Grundtvig DSE, we demonstrate a pathway towards more efficient, scalable, and reproducible annotation processes, and ultimately, this project affirms the potential of HITL methodologies to bridge traditional humanistic methods with computational innovations. While this study focuses on Grundtvig's corpus, future iterations could refine ML models for diverse textual traditions, particularly texts from the 19th century.

References

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- Rasmussen, Krista S. G., Kim Steen Ravn, Jon Tafdrup, and Katrine Frøkjær Baunvig (2023). "The Case for Scholarly Editions." In *Book of Proceedings, Digital Humanities in the Nordic and Baltic Countries, Sixth Conference*, 401–405.

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Biblia, / Det er / Den ganske/ Hell. Skriftes / Bøger, / Ved / Hans Kongl. Majests. / Vor allernaadigste Arve-Herres / Kong Christian / Den Syvendes / Christelige Omsorg, / med Flid og efter Grund-Texten efterseete og rettede ? [sic] saa / og med mange Paralleler og udførlige Summarier forsynede (1787). Copenhagen.

Passim. <https://github.com/dasmiq/passim>.